

6G-REFERENCE

Brand Guidelines

www.australo.org

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Brand Strategy

Vision

6G-REFERENCE envisions a future where urban areas are equipped with sustainable solutions that can cope with the ever-increasing traffic demands and population densification, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of sense.

This future is achievable through the development of ultra-dense cell-free deployments for joint coherent communications and sensing at cm-waves, which balance the benefits of sub-6GHz (e.g. reduced pathloss) and mm-wave (e.g. wide bandwidth) ranges.

6G-REFERENCE is committed to developing integrated circuit and antenna component solutions that address all of these challenges.

Mission

At 6G-REFERENCE, the mission is to develop cutting-edge integrated circuit and antenna component solutions that enable ultra-dense cell-free deployments for joint coherent communications and sensing at cm-waves.

We believe that our solutions will play a critical role in addressing the five fundamental challenges faced by these systems.

We are committed to designing frequency/time synchronization circuits and a new continuous synchronization framework based on full-duplex. Our goal is to provide a sustainable solution for urban areas that can cope with the ever-increasing traffic demands and population densification, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of sense.

Target Audience

Target persona 1

Gender: Female

Age: 25-30

Profession: Automotive Engineer

Education: Master's degree in Automotive Engineering

Project: Developing a new wireless communication technology for the automotive industry. By leveraging advanced cell-free deployments, we can balance the benefits of sub-6GHz and mm-wave ranges. Our technology addresses the challenges faced by these systems, including accurate synchronization among distributed radio units, fronthaul data distribution, integration of sensing capabilities, low complexity/cost/consumption radios, and coexistence with other services.

Target persona 2

Gender: Male

Age: 40-45

Profession: City Planner

Education: Master's degree in Architecture

Project: Developing a new wireless communication technology for smart cities. Our technology addresses the challenges faced by these systems, including accurate synchronization among distributed radio units, fronthaul data distribution, integration of sensing capabilities, low complexity/cost/consumption radios, and coexistence with other services. We are committed to developing integrated circuit and antenna component solutions that address all of these challenges.

Target persona 3

Gender: Male

Age: 20-25

Profession: Healthcare Professional

Education: Master's degree in Healthcare Engineering

Project: Developing a new wireless communication technology for the healthcare industry. Our technology addresses the challenges faced by these systems, including accurate synchronization among distributed radio units, fronthaul data distribution, integration of sensing capabilities, low complexity/cost/consumption radios, and coexistence with other services. We are committed to developing integrated circuit and antenna component solutions that address all of these challenges.

Personality

Archetypes

6G-REFERENCE is a brand that is committed to developing cutting-edge solutions for the challenges faced by ultra-dense cell-free deployments.

Our brand is built on the foundation of three archetypes: The Creator, The Explorer, and The Sage.

The Creator

6G-REFERENCE is innovative and imaginative, always pushing the boundaries of what is possible. They are constantly coming up with new ideas and solutions to complex problems.

The Creator archetype is driven by a desire to innovate and create something new. They are not afraid to take risks and are always looking for ways to improve upon existing technologies.

They are highly skilled in their field and are always seeking to learn more. The Creator is a visionary who is able to see beyond the present and into the future.

Goal: To innovate and create something new.

Strategy: To take risks and improve upon existing technologies.

Brand message: We are always pushing the boundaries of what is possible.

The Explorer

6G-REFERENCE is always looking for new ways to explore and discover. They are curious and adventurous, always seeking out new challenges and opportunities.

The Explorer archetype is driven by a desire to explore the unknown and to discover new possibilities. They are highly adaptable and are able to navigate complex situations with ease.

They are not afraid to take risks and are always looking for ways to push the boundaries of what is possible. The Explorer is a trailblazer who is able to chart new paths and explore new frontiers.

Goal: To explore the unknown and to discover new possibilities.

Strategy: To take risks and push the boundaries of what is possible.

Brand message: Always looking for new ways to explore and discover.

The Sage

6G-REFERENCE is wise and knowledgeable, with a deep understanding of the world around them. They are always seeking to learn more and share their knowledge with others.

The Sage archetype is driven by a desire to understand the world and to share that understanding with others. They are highly skilled in their field and are able to provide valuable insights and guidance to others.

They are patient and empathetic, and are always willing to help others learn. The Sage is a mentor who is able to guide others and help them achieve their goals.

Goal: To understand the world and to share that understanding with others.

Strategy: To provide valuable insights and guidance to others.

Brand message: We are always seeking to learn more and share our knowledge with others.

Visual Tools

Logo

Main version

6G ✦ REFERENCE

6G ✦ REFERENCE

Logo

Secondary versions

6G+REFERENCE

6G+REFERENCE

6G+REFERENCE

6G+REFERENCE

Color

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand

The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or black.

The primary color is the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color. The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color. Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors and their contrast ratio*

Source:

www.w3.org/TR/WCAG20/#visual-audio-contrast

Dark Cornflower Blue ^{Primary}

#1C487D

R28 G72 B125

C96 M73 Y24 K9

Contrast Ratio 9.24:1 AAA

White ^{Neutral}

#FFFFFF

R255 G255 B255

C0 M0 Y0 K0

21.00:1 AAA

Black ^{Neutral}

#000000

R0 G0 B0

C0 M0 Y0 K100

21.00:1 AAA

Maximum Blue Green ^{Secondary}

#1CCAC9

R28 G202 B201

C67 M0 Y29 K0

10.34:1 AAA

Metallic Seaweed ^{Secondary}

#1C89A3

R28 G137 B163

C79 M28 Y27 K7

4.07:1 AA

Yellow Orange ^{Accent}

#FFB430

R255 G180 B48

C0 M35 Y85 K0

11.82:1 AAA

Color

Gradient table

Specification of the gradient table

The gradient table indicates which neutral color (black or white) to use for writing text based on the percentage of opacity.

Refer to the adjacent table for more information.

100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------

80%	80%	80%	80%	80%
60%	60%	60%	60%	60%
40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
20%	20%	20%	20%	20%

Typography

Title

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

DOWNLOAD FONT: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Rajdhani>

Aa

Titles

Rajdhani Bold

**Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz**

0123456789

[(@#%\$^&)]"<>!?

Typography

Paragraph

The font displayed on the page is intended for use in paragraphs only.

DOWNLOAD FONT: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Rajdhani>

Aa Bb

Rajdhani Medium

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Mockups

5G + REFERENCE

Title Example

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Title Example

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Title Example

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Title Example

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Brand Guidelines

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